

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDIFUNA****FIRST NAME: MOHAMMED****PROGRAM CODE : DCTD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Type INSTRUCTOR LAST NAME****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 100% original

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401

1. Which of the following correctly explains the difference between *Limitation* and *Delimitation* as used in research?

- While limitations set the boundary, delimitations remove the boundary.
- While limitations are the unexpected circumstances that constrain the interpretation of the dissertation research findings, the delimitations are anticipated constraints in interpreting the dissertation research results.¹**
- While the imitations are factors within your control, delimitations are factors beyond your control as a researcher.
- None of these are correct.

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Second Edition) (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 49, 59.

2. Researchers should avoid research questions.
- If the answers to such questions are merely speculative.
 - If the answers to such questions require different capacities from the researcher's.
If the researcher cannot plausibly disprove the answer to such questions.
 - Apply All the answers are correct.²**
3. Which of the following statements relates to factorial validity?
- Concerns the congruence between what an instrument or test measures or is intended to measure.
 - Provides evidence that the content of the measure is congruent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the instrument, test, questionnaire, structured interview, semi-structured interview, focus group, journal, written, visual, auditory, or tactile exercise, or observation.³**
 - Provides evidence that the measure's total, content, or factor-derived scale scores are associated with other measures of similar, or somewhat similar, constructs in a theoretically consistent direction.
 - Documents the evidence that clusters of empirically associated items can be identified and reproduced across norm groups in a manner consistent with the conceptual or theoretical basis of the measure.

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition, vol. 45 (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 27, 28.

³ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)*, 41.

4. Which of the following factors should the research consider when evaluating sources of information?
- Whether a reputable press published the source.
 - Whether the book or article is peer-reviewed.
 - Whether the author is a reputable scholar.
 - All the above.**⁴
5. Which Chicago citation styles are provided in the Turabian Manual?
- Parenthetical style and narrative style.
 - Author-date style and notes-bibliography style.**⁵
 - Source-date style and author-bibliography style.
 - Author-source style and note-citation style.
6. Which of the following statements apply to the research problem?
- They can be classified as either a conceptual or practical problem.
 - The condition of a conceptual problem is a knowledge gap, and its cost is the consequence of a lack of knowledge.
 - The condition of a practical problem is any state of affairs that troubles the researcher or his readers.

⁴ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 45:42.

⁵ Ibid., 45:144.

All the answers are correct.⁶

7. Identify and select from the options below the citation style documented in the Turabian Manual.

Harvard style.

Chicago style.⁷

American Psychological Association (APA) style.

Modern Language Association (MLA) style.

8. Which of the following is irrelevant when drafting the *final introduction*?

The area of future research.⁸

Opening context or background.

A statement of your research question or your research problem's condition.

A statement of the significance of your question.

9. Select from the options below the correct paraphrasing advice.

Must be your words.

Your writing style to express the author's ideas must differ from the author's style.

The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of

⁶ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition, vol. 45 (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 27, 28.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack*, Fourth Edition. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 41.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 45:111.

what the author originally wrote.

All are correct.⁹

10. Which of these three circumstances is not a valid ground for not citing a source? Select all that are correct.

When hen the information you are writing about is common knowledge that others can access in numerous areas, you do not need to cite its source.¹⁰

When you have already cited the author many times, and it is unnecessary to cite again.

When ideas are similar to your own, and therefore are as good as your own.

When the idea is paraphrased and appears different.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack*, 36.

¹⁰ Ibid.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.